

MAKING AND ENACTING POSSIBLE FUTURES: SANDQUERY AS A VEHICLE FOR EMBODIED INTERACTION

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ABSTRACT

So much of the world is out of control; it can be overwhelming, terrifying or beautiful. Though chaotic emotions are often difficult to share, creative expression can be a vehicle for understanding and communicating these emotions. "Sandplay is one of many creative therapies to use an expressive form of communication" (Malchiodi, 2005). Sandquery is a kinesthetic method for generative design research that is adapted from Sandplay, a method of psychotherapy. Future-based prompts given to participants are summarized to illustrate Sandquery's potential for creative embodied interactions that inform design and emotion. In addition, my research with Enactavision, a virtual variation of Sandquery, seeks to advance current knowledge and understanding of the intertwined relationship between motion and emotion.

Keywords: generative design research, methods, embodied interaction, emotion, psychology

INTRODUCTION

On a personal level, emotion drives us all. No matter who you are, you can't escape from feelings of anger, joy and sadness. If you are lucky, you learn to accept your conditions, no matter how chaotic, and grow to creatively generate new ideas about moving on and pursuing happiness. Sometimes our emotions are triggered by circumstances beyond our control, and we find feelings difficult to communicate. Some psychoanalysts would argue our bodies in motion are more suited to express feelings than are thoughts and words. "Often the hands know how to solve a riddle with which the intellect has wrestled in vain" (Jung,

1969). The beginning of this paper introduces terms from research that are not native to design. These concepts are introduced to broaden existing methods employed for generative design research.

POSSIBLE INFLUENCES OF USING PSYCHOANALYTIC TOOLS IN DESIGN RESEARCH

Generative design research is a way of involving people early in the design process. People "are asked to make designerly artefacts to express aspects of their situation, their life, their worries and joys, etc." (Stappers and Sanders, 2003). Generative design research practitioners can adopt and learn from the tools and methods used in expressive psychotherapies to establish conditions for creativity and co-learning. Psychoanalytic tools and methods can be used to evoke ideas by using motion and subsequent emotion as drivers in a generative process. The therapist learns how s/he may guide a client to honest expression by observation, probing, providing expressive tools, and teaching cognitive strategies. Expressive or creative therapies, tools and techniques are engaging, creative and fun. In a similar but unique way, the generative design researcher can facilitate individual or group opportunity-mapping activities by borrowing successful strategies from psychotherapy.

PSYCHOTHERAPY AND THE EMBODIED MIND

People seek out psychotherapy when they are having a hard time coping with emotions in an uncertain time. On a micro-level, these uncertainties, crises and chaotic events can come in the form of loss, disease, and trauma. One might try a therapy to feel better, enticed by the possibility of moving on to new stages of the grieving cycle. With guidance, one explores the

expression of a range of emotions. Therapy can involve sharing and co-thinking with a professional – a typical method of psychoanalysis is the "talking cure". Freud said that, "words are the essential tool of mental treatment" (Freud, 1890). Something modern analytical psychology is trying to understand is the "paradox of how human minds are quintessentially bounded and unique, while at the same time quintessentially unbounded and connected" (Mayer, 2002). Enactivism, a developing direction within embodied cognition (McGann and Torrance, 2005) explores these intricate connections. This enactive approach is related to expressive psychoanalytic methods because some creative psychotherapies incorporate body movement, visual, spatial, musical, interpersonal and/or intrapersonal interaction(s). Our mind and body influence each other and how these inner-communications are working requires more research. "We are not rocks in a stream of experience, but agents actively involved with our environment, our world" (McGann and Torrance, 2005). In the field of education, scholar Howard Gardner proposed a theory of multiple intelligences. He outlines several kinds: Logical-mathematical, Spatial, Linguistic, Bodily-kinesthetic, Musical, Interpersonal, Intrapersonal, Naturalistic, and Existential. Gardner's research connects with the theory of embodiment, as he considers bodily-kinesthetic knowledge a form of problem solving. "The ability to use one's body to express an emotion (as in a dance), to play a game (as in a sport), or to create a new product (as in devising an invention) is evidence of the cognitive features of body usage" (Gardner, 1993).

EMPATHY, EMOTION AND EMBODIED INTERACTION

"Interpersonal intelligence allows one to understand and work with others. Intrapersonal intelligence allows one to understand and work with oneself" (Gardner, 1993). These two intelligences could also be called empathy with others and empathy with oneself. Enactivists believe "empathy is understood as omnipresent, a unique form of intentionality, directing the self toward the other's experience" (Jungmann, 2011). Jungmann researched embodied cognition and creativity extensively and summarized the enactive approach relative to emotion and her findings are relevant to generative design research. "Emotion is

considered a feature in the action perception cycle, mostly via non-conscious brain and body states. As such it is endogenously initiated and outwardly directed through behaviour and, like perception, it is dependent on intentional action" (Jungmann, 2011). To put it simply, a theory of embodiment implies that when we are intentionally moving our bodies we are more empathetic and more able to communicate our emotions compared to when we are not moving our bodies intentionally. Gardner notes that intrapersonal intelligence is the most private of all the intelligences and "some other expressive form", like music, writing or dance, is required if the observer is to detect it at work. Therefore, the most emotive, private and empathetic forms of expression require an intentional action via expressive form to be understood by others. "Enactive cognitive science attributes empathy to the innate understanding of intersubjectivity. Rather than empathy with oneself, artists must find ways to understand empathically the consequences of their creative preparations for others to experience creative participation" (Jungmann, 2011). Empathy and emotions can be embodied and communicated via expressive forms like Sandplay therapy.

SANDPLAY THERAPY

The tools and methods of expressive therapies are broad, derived from various art therapies using music, visual arts, dance and/or play. Sandplay therapy, a method of psychotherapy and personal development (Kalff, 2003), is a "powerful tool to deal with many life events including traumas, relationship matters, personal growth, integration and transformation of the Self..." (Boik and Goodwin, 2000). Sandplay therapy is one expressive therapy successfully used with children and clients unable to express themselves verbally due to trauma and intense emotional experiences. "Not only does the client re-experience the trauma as s/he recreates, but s/he also frequently moves stuck emotional and physical energy as s/he uses her/his hands to move the sand and manipulate the figures in the tray" (Boik and Goodwin, 2000). Playing in a sandbox – at first glance – may look juvenile, but what may be happening subconsciously can be exciting and worth exploring. In a sand tray, people are able to spatially and kinesthetically map out ideas and/or problems. By playing, they express feelings brought about by an experience. They also can creatively problem solve by generating new ideas

and opportunities that bring acceptance to one's feelings about circumstances. The inherent attributes of Sandplay can be related to information a design researcher is seeking.

Creative psychotherapies reveal opportunities for design researchers to learn more about embodied interaction and its relationship to creativity and opportunity-mapping. The goal is to explore new tools and methods that identify problems and go to a deeper level, provoking interactions that require movement for expression and create opportunities for unique embodied emotional expressions to co-create future scenarios.

SANDQUERY AS A GENERATIVE DESIGN RESEARCH METHOD

Sandquery, adapted from Sandplay, is a human-centered method for generative design research and an activity for communicating and learning with others.

Sandquery engages people in making, telling and enacting (Sanders, Brandt and Binder, 2010). This method allows people to explore the freedom of individual expression within a group activity and allows opportunities to make connections to others' expressions. This opportunity for autonomous kinesthetic expression within a group is an advantage over word and thought-based group brainstorming often dominated by extroverts and people who excel at language-based activities. People using Sandquery can give form to individual emotional expression and experience empathy with their teammates' built world, artifacts and enactments.

The tools of Sandquery include a sand tray, sand, objects and water. The Sandquery sand tray is a wooden box measuring approximately 20" x 30" x 3". The bottom and interior sides of the tray are painted light blue. The tray is filled halfway with sand. The figures, or objects, to be manipulated inside the tray can be natural (leaves, sticks), man-made (wire pipe cleaners, small toys). As in Sandplay, Sandquery can be successful with or without objects or water. There is great significance to the use of sand and water (Okada, 2006), the dimensions of the tray, the tray's interior color (Zhou, 1999), and the symbolic language of miniatures and objects (Boik and Goodwin, 2000).

Patterned from Sandplay, objects chosen for Sandquery represent the human experience and are categorized into people, animals, plant life, minerals, transportation, etc. (Boik and Goodwin, 2000). The object count for initial Sandquery sessions was well beyond 200 and these will be described in more detail later.

Generative design research is interested in methods that evoke, in particular, emotional expression. Embodied cognition research is interested in people's sensory-motor abilities and their relationship to many facets of life, including expression, emotion and learning. The tangible expressions created by people using Sandquery are manifested visually, spatially, and with body-based interactions. After a scene is made, people tell a story about their scene and as researchers we learn from these stories. To explore Sandquery as a possible method I designed a qualitative study enabling "participatory envisioning and enactment by setting users in future situations" (Sanders, Brandt and Binder, 2010). This study explored a new generative design research method that elicits both emotional and cognitive data: the Sandquery method fosters the expression of deep, primordial intuitive reasoning. Feelings and desires are communicated via embodied interaction. Sandquery, like Sandplay, is an expressive activity and can be a vehicle for emotional communication. Chaotic and macro-level themes were elicited from this study.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Thirteen Sandquery sessions were conducted and documented in May 2010 at OSU. The theme of "Design in 2030" was used for all sessions. At the beginning of each session, participants were prompted with a series of queries:

- In the year 2030, what do designers do?
- How will they improve the world?
- What's their role?
- What's the world like?

The participants were given time to reflect on the prompts and work with the tools. After a period of time, they were asked to present their creations. These presentations were video recorded.

PARTICIPANTS

Twenty-three people contributed to the Sandquery sessions. Some sessions included one person and others included two to eight people working on the given queries simultaneously. All participants were designers at OSU: nine Department of Design faculty, two graduate design students and twelve undergraduate design students.

OBSERVATIONS FROM THE STUDY

At the start of a Sandquery session, many people get quiet to take time to explore, build and imagine privately. They explore the tools by touching them; gestures are made as they interact with the sand and toys in intricate patterns. Their eyes and imaginations seem to paint possibilities of what could be.

Sandquery can be used by one person working independently and groups of people playing alone or with others. Regardless, the activity stimulates the creative process.

While observing groups using Sandquery, I found the activity tends to be represented by one of two extremes: loud, verbal and collaborative or quiet and introspective including limited collaboration.

People sometimes enact during a Sandquery session but enactments are not always narrated verbally. A person personifying a toy snake through movement and by pretending “you” are the snake in the sand tray would be considered enactment. This may or may not include a dialogue of how the toy snake is thinking and or feeling. What is happening between the participant and tools is a private interaction within her/his own imagination. When the researcher concludes the building time, participants add final touches to their made forms; they awake as if from a dream and begin to tell their story or idea.

After the scene is built, some creators narrate a complex story, unraveling each character's role and connection to the built environment. The stories tend to be abstract but are not difficult to understand with each participant's explanation. While telling their stories participants often gesture to parts of the scene and sometimes touch elements and characters with roles in the story.

Problem Finding and Problem Solving

The creative challenge of Sandquery is dependent on the researcher's queries. The prompts may stimulate problem-solving and problem-finding opportunities for participants. Is there a relationship between creativity and problem seeking? There is not agreement in literature as to what happens when a person engages in creative activities. However, “Creativity research operates from the assumption that creativity is a form of problem-solving” (Jungmann, 2011). In Sandquery, problem-finding and problem-solving are embodied interactions. A person's hand and finger movements become the director of the story in the sand.

Generative methods for design-led research that require enactment may enable creativity due to the tools engaging the participant's sensorimotor processes. "There is considerable evidence that reasoning and problem-solving make heavy use of sensorimotor stimulation" (Wilson, 2002).

Sandquery and Enactment

A person's intentional movements transform the sand, build the sand up, create burrows and fill them with water. A person's movements also project feelings through the interaction of the sand and objects. These miniature versions of animals, people, and nature take on new meanings with each new person interacting with Sandquery. These miniatures interact in the built environment within the sand tray according to the will of the person. The characters walk on paths, fly, are buried and are finally set to a stationary place as another object begins to tell its own narrative – often incorporating the story of the other objects previously set to temporary motion. It has been observed that one person may be pretending with their own miniature and as they empathize with their held character, they begin to play and communicate with another person's character. To put it simply, the people in this Sandquery scenario are pretending together. They are pretending with tangible objects to design a miniature world that holds all the natural and human complexity of the real world. In the Sandquery space, people are able to empathize, express ideas, learn and communicate while interacting in a visual, tangible story.

Understanding Sandquery Data

In Sandquery, for the most part, people spend time with one or two objects at a time. With words and/or motions, they spend a great amount of energy telling about each character, the character's connection to the environment and its relationship to other characters in the macro-level story. The trouble seems to be that more than two relationships are impossible to enact simultaneously due to the limitations of tangible tools. The enactments that occur using the tools of Sandquery can be understood by an observer if the participant annotates the meaning of objects, motions and the composition verbally. Like Sandplay, Sandquery can be an introspective, expressive activity that, in its purest form, is a non-verbal, kinesthetic activity. Lastly, Sandquery participants present their scene verbally and sometimes with gesture. In the interpretation of Sandquery, qualitative researchers rely on audio transcripts of video recordings to uncover insights and themes from Sandquery sessions.

CHAOTIC THEMES AND MEANINGFUL INSIGHTS FROM SANDQUERY SESSIONS

Of the 13 sessions prompted by what designers will do 20 years into the future, in the year 2030, the Sandquery presentations represented utopian themes, chaotic themes as well as neutral, matter-of-fact themes. These thematic summaries were developed by reviewing and analyzing video recordings and transcripts of Sandquery participants' presentations after the scene has been made. The themes revealed are heartfelt expressions about the role of design in the future. The four sessions highlighted below were chosen as examples that illustrate how different people and groups have interacted with Sandquery materials. The summaries briefly detail how much time and talking occurred during the early making phase, and also make note of how the creators interacted with their teammates, when applicable.

"HIDDEN BEAUTIES TO BE DISCOVERED"

In this individual session, a 25-year-old male graduate student in design shared his high hopes for the future

Figure 1. Photograph of final scene, "Hidden beauties to be discovered". One person's Sandquery scene.

of design. The composition (Figure 1) in the sand tray was symmetrical, using mostly marbles and seashells and the largest object was placed in the center. This student was very engaged in the activity, working for about 20 minutes silently. He began to verbalize the meanings of the finger-drawn circles in the sand surrounded by several marbles hidden within seashells. The marbles are "hidden beauties to be discovered," he explained. When asked about what kind of beauty, he said, "I mean not... on some deep, deep, deep sense of things or needs, or activities, something like that. Not just some superficial kinds of things, material, or just making money." His verbalization is abstract and is open to interpretation. When he describes the object (an embroidered compact mirror) in the very center of the sand tray, he says it could be the world, the cosmos. He explained that it's a "great, great beauty, and it affects everything, some kind of spiritual kind of thinking about design." His expression is a powerful example of more aspirational forms of generative design research. According to this participant, the future of design will be more beautiful, meaningful, and spiritual than it is now.

"WE ARE DESTROYING THE WORLD"

The next session (Figure 2) included a team of one male and one female Department of Design faculty members who are also practicing industrial designers. The composition within the sand tray changed iteratively for about 15 minutes as they explained a narrative together, while taking polite turns, about how current design systems work chaotically. The final composition represented a more sustainable system

that described an ideal way of living achieved by better design. Speaking about how things are now, one said, "What we do is product design without responsibility and accountability. We are destroying the world." The team of two used a lot of gesturing with and without the materials of Sandquery to uncover possibilities for the future role of design. Not a lot of time was spent in quiet reflection, and they worked out the prompt by playing with the materials and engaging in a dialogue with each other throughout the session.

The synopsis for this session is that designers have an opportunity to act as physicians to a materialistic culture, prescribing an attitude change in relation to consumption and production. The design can be a "catalyst to simplifying things and to remove or deal with complexity." Designers are also synthesizers, as they think they have a better understanding of many factors, like psychology and ergonomics, as compared to engineers. As a team, these two participants saw little hope in discovering more unmet, materialistic needs. This team saw designers of the future as translators in a culture ill with consumption. As one person said, "I think that primarily we want to change the context in which industrial design has operated. It is not about meeting ridiculous needs... like just changing the style of the car every year so people have ...a never-ending thing ...the same mindset, the same skills and ability apply to more productive and meaningful things." This team's hopeful silver lining is achieved by applying well-rounded design talent to create designs that not only appeal to vanity but are meaningful, useful and ecologically-responsible.

Figure 2. Photograph of final scene, "We are destroying the world". Two people's Sandquery scene.

Figure 3. Photograph of final scene, "I think that we will be inspiring change". Four people's Sandquery scene.

"I THINK THAT WE WILL BE INSPIRING CHANGE"

The following session (Figure 3) is composed of four creators: two males and two female undergraduate students all studying industrial design. As the prompt was being read, one of the students sectioned the sand tray into four equal quadrants by drawing a giant plus sign in the sand using his finger. The teammates worked silently with the materials within their individual quadrants of the sand tray. Even though they didn't speak to each other, they were keeping tabs of each other's designs visually, by taking time from their own building to watch what their neighbors were doing with the materials. At this point, they were unaware of the exact meaning of their neighbors' scenes. When they had worked silently for more than 15 minutes, they were asked to put finishing touches on their creations. At this time, one of the male creators began building a path made of rocks to only two of the three neighboring worlds. Later he said, "The rocks, I just connected everyone's paths, because I think somehow, I'm not sure how, but I think designers can help make a stronger sense of community through design." He explained that he intentionally did not build a path to one of the creator's worlds and even formed a mound of sand to better separate the two adjacent quadrants more severely. The quadrant from which he separated his own looked the most materialistic: a house pointed away from the center with a pile of the shiniest available objects in front of the house.

During the explanation part of the session, the path-builder creator said, "And then this mound, I didn't know what he was going for originally, I thought his

was more of a materialistic deal, so I was just kinda separating myself from him. But I found out that wasn't exactly what he was going for." The other creator's world looked materialistic, but he said that was his intent. The "materialistic" creator explained his scene before the other three creators and expressed this desire: "Hopefully, in the future, design will not be centered towards fancy material possessions." He went on to say that design has an opportunity to create systems to solve existing problems. He said, "Designing systems, you know, less tangible things... would create a bigger impact than just a product itself."

So one by one, the participants explained their concepts for the future of design and the future role of designers. One quadrant focused on the communication of different kinds of designers: builders, nature experts, and abstract designers. These three kinds of designers work together to find and solve problems, explained the participant, when she said, "I feel like design can only be accomplished when everyone collaborates together." The next creator to explain her quadrant describes living in harmony with nature in terms of energy, food and recreation. She predicts that design will veer away from "sketching all day for pretty things to sell" but instead use these creative skills for meaningful purposes, such as building public facilities, like a library, in a developing community. The fourth person to explain his world was the path-builder, mentioned previously. He talked specifically about the role of designers in the future and said, "I think that we will be inspiring change...". The change of which he speaks is an appeal to consider the long-term impact of chosen design materials. We as designers must be mindful and responsible for what will "end up in a landfill." This theme of divorcing ourselves from vain consumerism is abundant in many of the 13 sessions. The creator with the visually materialistic quadrant reiterates this role of the future designer. He said, "I guess I would put them (designers) in the category of way-finders, to guide people to a better ideal and a better idea as to how they live their lives and not do it though fancy products."

Figure 4. Photograph of final scene, "We have a problem: everything's water". Eight people's Sandquery scene.

"WE HAVE A PROBLEM: EVERYTHING'S WATER"

The most exciting, loud and chaotically-themed session (Figure 4) is the result of eight undergraduate students collaborating for approximately 30 minutes using Sandquery. These students, five female and three male, were all studying industrial design. From the moment it was this group's turn to play, there was a frenzy of motion, noise and wide eyes. Some of the time, creators started by manipulating the sand, building it up and digging trenches. Others inspected the miniature toys and objects.

They scanned for uniquely meaningful toys and objects and some creators even hoarded his or her favorites; objects were safely cupped in their hands or put off to the side in a pile, with the intention of placing them within the scene later. From the beginning, they worked as a team excitedly, building both individually and adding onto others' built-up areas, all which symbolize a part in the big narrative. The flurry of words, gestural movements, fondling of materials, and collaborative communication resembled an unruly marketplace in the sense that observers could scarcely make out what was happening behind the blurs and squawks. This collaboration could have become an iterative process taking hours if time had been more flexible; however, about 20 minutes into the activity's start, the group was encouraged to wrap-up their Sandquery scene.

The first creator to speak began the explanation of the micro-world by saying, "We started creating things, like a bridge, and we sort of fed off one another." Like a tour guide, the second creator pointed and said,

"And see, this is the capital island, and there are people guarding all the bridges." The third creator to chime in got straight to the point when s/he said, "We have a problem: everything's water. And then we found a solution." Others go on to point out different places within the community of the visually-chaotic scene: the pharmacy, the barbershop, the church, the park, the military, houses, the airport, the zoo, etc." The students created a water-world, a world with more water than land, and this led to specific problems. One participant explained, "It's very crowded...we can't really live...you have to work together, because you're in such tight quarters." In this world, designers are important. Designers work to solve all the problems that this world experiences. When asked about what designers of the future do exactly, the same thing was said in a couple of different ways; they all expounded on a shared group theme over and over again. One creator said, "I mean, I kinda just see us designing how society functions and all of the facets of society we have to be involved in." Another followed up by saying, "And we have to work with all different facets, even religious. And figure-out how to get everything organized." Another went on to say, "We (designers) are catering to your need for nature, transportation, protection, religious answers, housing, sickness, and happiness."

SANDQUERY CONCLUSIONS

Our world as it exists now and many of its frightening realities were themes in these future-based sessions that used Sandquery as a springboard for generative design research. The materials of Sandquery are simple, but they provide rich tools for expression. Through embodied interaction, the creators of these 13 sessions, whether working in a group or alone, were able to quickly tackle a complex set of future-based questions and provide unique explanations by visualizing, annotating and enacting relationships that arguably would have been impossible to express with only paper and pen.

ENACTAVISON: A VIRTUAL METHOD FOR EMBODIED INTERACTION

Research with Sandquery has informed a new virtual environment that requires embodied interaction for creative expression. This research is exploratory and will be briefly explained. Sandquery evoked

emotionally-rich data. And by watching people play with Sandquery I couldn't help but wonder what would happen if more than two objects could be enacted (moving intentionally), would the story get more complex, more expressive? "There is a need within human-computer interaction to learn more about embodied interaction" (Antle, 2011). Enactavision (I coined the name before researching enactivism) is a virtual interactive environment that enables co-learning by engaging people in futuristic problem-solving activities using enactment with a multi-touch table, large-scale wall projection, and Kinect gesture tracking.

DESIGNING FOR VIRTUAL EMBODIED INTERACTION

When the Enactavision design team began the design process of a virtual environment inspired by Sandquery, (my advisors, student colleagues and I are responsible for Enactavision's design and interaction programming), the act of embodying the motion of multiple characters in a Sandquery-like ephemeral quality became the interface's main objective. Creating a virtual replica of Sandquery was never the goal at the beginning stages of Enactavision's development. This is because a virtual replica of Sandplay, "Sandplay on an Interactive Tabletop" (Hancock, et. al, 2010), has already been successfully developed by a team of researchers and psychoanalysts, so there is no point in replicating Sandquery in a virtual mode. By choosing some positive embodied attributes observed in Sandquery, the early designs for Enactavision explore embodying a virtual character that mimics a participant's real-time movements. Allowing the creators to embody virtual characters in real-time is the essence of the interaction. Enactavision supports one to three players. No matter if the activity is collaborative or done alone, up to two people have control of one object at a time; the virtual characters mirror the movements of the participant(s). The interface allows a participant to record, stop recording and playback the motion of a virtual character. Each recorded layer of animation contains a character or background element that is a part of the bigger story. The final result is a scene on a projected screen with many layers of enacted objects. Enacting multiple layers of objects beyond two at a time is the unique interaction

that is impossible in the physical world but is made possible by a virtual world. Due to intentional movement required to use Enactavision, the animated layers are meaningful and illustrate the participant(s)' embodied interaction.

NEXT STEPS IN THESIS RESEARCH

The exciting part of developing a new participatory design research method like Enactavision is assessing it in relation to other research methods. The next step in my research is to compare and contrast the process and insights gained from four design research methods: Sandquery, Enactavision (i.e., both new methods), paper collage and focus group (i.e., both established methods).

Figure 5. The Participatory Prototyping Cycle. (Sanders, E.B.-N. and Stappers, P.J., 2012 expected.)

Different methods were chosen based on where they are on the Participatory Prototyping Cycle (PPC), (figure 5). The PPC diagram represents the form of participatory design research methods or tools, "Form describes the kind of action that is taking place between the participants in an activity, and is described as making, telling and/or enacting" (Sanders, Brandt and Binder, 2010). Instead of trying to virtually replicate Sandquery, a conscious decision was made early in the design process to make enactment the primary input for Enactavision. This purposefully creates differences between Sandquery and Enactavision so that the comparison may be more interesting. This qualitative study will share between methods an open-ended prompt that sets participants in the same future situation. Because design research methods elicit both positive and negative feelings from participants, it will be interesting to design researchers to see how four different methods (Enactavision, Sandquery, paper

collage, and a focus group) compare and contrast. I am currently conducting this comparative research and its findings will be reported in my thesis.

CONCLUSIONS

Generative design researchers can successfully borrow and adopt tools and techniques from expressive therapies belonging to psychoanalysis. By using new embodied interactive methods, participants in the design process are given appropriate tools and techniques to express emotions that go beyond how one merely feels about a product or service. Participants who use Sandquery are able to emote macro-level future desires and aspirations by engaging their bodily-kinesthetic, spatial, intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligences. They are able to find and solve problems creatively whether working alone, in a quiet group, or in a vocal, collaborative group.

Exploring tools, techniques and methods that evoke and capture the expression of emotion is paramount to this human-centered research. There is much to gain through research about our emotions, embodied minds and the role of sensorimotor interactions in relation to the creative process, learning, and collaboration. The high-level goal of this research is that through generative design-led research we can begin to collectively design the future to be more beautiful, meaningful, responsible and spiritual than it is now. Design insights expressed via enactment are sincere expressions of our brightest hopes and our darkest fears for our possible futures.

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